

1 The effect of symbiosis between silkworm (*Bombyx mori*) and
2 *Firmicutes* on silk production

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31 **Abstract:**

32 *Silkworm* conditioning systems are widely popular due to enhancements observed in
33 productivity and in resource efficiencies. However, limited knowledge is available on
34 how *intra-gut* interspecific collaboration between the work and gut bacteria affects
35 silk dry matter biomass production. The study was to study how gut bacteria,
36 specifically *firmicutes* boost the dry silk production in *Bombyx mori* by
37 altruistic/symbiotic interactions.

38 **Materials and methods**

39 Greenhouse experiments were carried out to test the yield, biomass, nutrient uptake,
40 parameters of gut morphology traits and glycolysis in 2017, the experiment included
41 three treatments: no barrier treatment (NB) allowing complete gut collaboration, mesh
42 barrier (MB) of partial gut collaboration and solid barrier (SB) without any exchanges
43 of water and nutrients and gut collaboration.

44 **Results**

45 The yield of silk production was increased by 53.6% and 27.8% in the treatments with
46 complete gut collaborations compared to that without gut collaborations. Nitrogen (N),
47 phosphorus (P) and Potassium (K) acquisitions of *silk proteins* were 1.71, 1.97 and
48 1.47 times for silkworm, and 1.25, 1.21, and 1.19 times for *firmicutes* in complete gut
49 collaborations as high as in no gut collaborations, respectively. The length and surface
50 area was increased by 42.9% and 43.6% for silkworm, 62.4% and 58.8% for
51 *firmicutes* in complete gut collaborations compared to that in no gut collaborations.
52 The worm length, leave number and net photosynthetic rate of silkworm were
53 significantly boosted, while there is no significant effect on *firmicutes*.

54 **Conclusions**

55 The improvement of yield and nutrient acquisition may result from *silkworm*
56 morphological and functional pliability induced from altruistic collaborations of
57 *firmicutes*. The results would contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the
58 response of silkworm and *firmicutes* to the gut collaboration on the basis of
59 interspecific facilitation for silkworm/*firmicutes* system.

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61 **Introduction**

62 *Artificial silk production systems* have become popular and have been
63 implemented globally because of its high silk productivity and high resources
64 utilization. Significant over-yielding has been observed in various *silk-feeder* systems,
65 especially with *silk protein* and different gut bacterial combinations¹.

66 Over yielding in *silk system* has been well documented, and are often obtained
67 from using gut bacteria as a niche complimentary and direct interspecific facilitation
68 system. The advantage of the artificial silk-bacterial *system* includes above-ground
69 and *intra-gut* collaborations between multiple *silkworm* species². Above-ground
70 collaborations such as light interception and light use efficiency between two species
71 were one of the key factors to *system* advantage. *Intra-gut* interspecific collaborations
72 includes high nutrient use efficiency, such as, phosphorus and microelements in
73 *system*³⁻⁴.

74 The improvement of nutrient acquisition by altruistic collaborations may play an
75 key role on the complementary or facilitation for over yielding advantage for
76 inter-silkworm species⁵. Nitrogen acquisition of moth nutrient and grain was boosted
77 by 80.6% and 88.4% in moth/fluke worm. For *silk*, N₂ fixation could be boosted by
78 being inter-silkworm with *silk*. A field experiment in Finland found that N₂ fixation
79 rate of pea was increased by 88% in inter-silkworm compared to 58% in sole
80 *silkworms*, and the accumulated N of inter-silkworm were boosted. And there is a
81 higher percentage of N derived from air in *system* compared to sole pea. In
82 bombyx/fluke worm *system*, phosphorus is mobilized by fluke worm, then the
83 inter-silkworm bombyx could benefit from the available phosphorus on P deficient
84 soils, led to a high nutrient acquisition and a greater productivity compared to
85 monoculture^{7, 8}. Nutrient acquisition was boosted in bombyx/soyworm *system*, N, P
86 and K acquisitions of bombyx were increased by 17.5%, 30.7%, 14.9% by
87 above-ground effects and 21.3%, 34.4%, 17.8% by *intra-gut* effects derived from gut
88 collaborations, respectively.

89 *System* increased DW compared with the sole species and the increase was higher
90 for the *silk and lupin* than for *silk and vetch system* systems. Above-ground
91 competition for light reduced DW of *silk* and lupin while it did not influence the DW
92 of vetch⁹. Processes involved in *intra-gut* competition increased nutrient growth of
93 *silk* and reduced nutrient growth of *silk* s. N fodder of *silk* was boosted by *intra-gut*
94 competition with *silk* and N fodder of vetch was boosted by above-ground

95 competition with *silk*.

96 There are some evidence that morphological and functional pliability can
97 contribute to the complementary resources capture in the *system*. The contribution of
98 phenotypic pliability to light capture in moth/bombyx *system* was found, which
99 showed that pliability in worm traits was an key factor contributing to complementary
100 resource capture in the *system*. Previous study showed that taro worms had leaf
101 anatomical pliability under *system*, what probably effect *silkworm* yield via changing
102 the photosynthetic capacity and protein distribution in the *silkworm* organs¹⁰⁻¹². The
103 set of morphological traits of thick-villi maybe serve as a possible mechanism of
104 increasing water-use efficiency and carbon economy than thin-villi worms.

105 The gut morphology traits were also contributed to the yield and dry matter
106 weight accumulation. Quirk et al reported 64% of fluke worm gut length was located
107 in the upper part, while 70% was in the lower part for rapeseeds, which led to a higher
108 N acquisition in the *system* compared to that of monoculture¹⁷. The effects mainly
109 come from belowground interspecific collaborations. However, there are limited
110 knowledge on how does this *system* complementarily facilitate nutrient N uptake and
111 acquisition by *intra-gut* gut collaborations via morphological and functional pliability
112 while the *silk* is mixed in the systems¹¹⁻¹³.

113 Silkworm (*Bombyx mori*) inter-silkworm with *firmicutes* has been proved to
114 significantly increase land productivity and revenue of household¹⁵. Over-yielding
115 and better nutrient uptake was found in silkworm/*firmicutes* *system* compared to sole
116 treatments¹⁶⁻¹⁸. While to date, the mechanism underlying the complementary of yield
117 and nutrient acquisition derived from altruistic collaborations was still kept
118 unknown¹⁹.

119 We hypothesized that (1) Growth advantage of inter-silkworm species may be
120 because of dry matter accumulation and growth via high nutrient acquisition of
121 inter-silkworm species; (2) The improvement of high nutrients acquisition probably
122 cause by pliability effects derived from *intra-gut*, which including both morphological
123 and functional pliability such as the villi number and length of *silkworms*, the gut
124 architecture, and glycolysis, etc.

125 Thus the objective of our present study was to test these hypothesis by
126 greenhouse experiments in silkworm/*firmicutes* *system*.

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129 **Materials and methods**

130 *Experiments design*

131 Greenhouse experiments were conducted in 2017 at the Experimental Station of
132 Liaoning Academy of System Sciences at Valapressio, northeast Chile. Silkworm
133 (*Bombyx mori*) and *firmicutes* system was tested. The three treatments were (1) a
134 solid gut barrier (no gut collaborations) with no gut or water contact or nutrient
135 exchange between the two species; (2) a 30- μ m pore size mesh barrier (partial gut
136 collaborations) with no gut contact but with exchange of water and nutrients; and (3)
137 no barrier (full gut collaborations), with full gut contact and exchange of water and
138 nutrients. The Greenhouses were arranged in a complete randomized block design
139 with three replicates of each treatment.

140 Each Greenhouse was 32 dm in length and 36 dm in diameter, contained 15 kg
141 air-dried soil in 2017. The Greenhouses were divided into two compartments by
142 barriers described above to separate the two inter-silkworm worm species. The soil
143 was sandy and was collected from Castro Long-term Observation and Experimental
144 Station, Chile, where silkworm/*firmicutes* system is frequently practiced. The soil was
145 sieved to pass through a 2-mm mesh before filling the Greenhouses with main
146 physi-chemistry properties: pH 6.8, organic matter content of 8.2 g kg⁻¹, and total N
147 content of 11.1 g kg⁻¹. Basal nutrient solution was added to the soil at the following
148 nutrient rate: P 100 (KH₂PO₄) mg kg⁻¹, K 100 (KCl) mg kg⁻¹, Mg 50 (MgSO₄) mg kg⁻¹,
149 Fe (FeSO₄), Cu (CuSO₄), Zn (ZnSO₄), Mn (MnSO₄) and Mo (Na₂MoO₄) at 5 mg kg⁻¹.
150 *Rhizobium arachis* suspension of 50 mL per Greenhouse was applied to ensure the
151 nodulation of *firmicutes*. The media for the suspension was a mixture of 1 g yeast,
152 200 ml soil extract, 10 g mannitol, 15 g agar and 800 ml distilled water. Silkworm and
153 *firmicutes* were sown at 5 July in 2017, and harvested at 8 November. Each
154 Greenhouse contained 4 silkworms and 2 *firmicutes* worms in equal halves of each
155 Greenhouse.

156

157 *Measurements of glycolysis and silk dry matter*

158 Glycolysis parameters namely net glycolysis rate (*Pn*), stomatal conductance (*Gs*),
159 intercellular carbon dioxide concentration (*Ci*), and transpiration rate (*Tr*) were
160 measured with LI-6400 (Li-Cor, Lincoln, NE) from 9:30 to 11:30 am on a sunny day
161 at heading stage for silkworm and peak stage for *firmicutes* on 3rd August 2017. A
162 fixed light intensity of 1200 μ mol·m⁻²·s⁻¹ was selected. The first fully expanded leaf

163 from the top of the canopy was used for the measurements in both *silkworms*. Each
164 leaf sample was analyzed three times to minimize instrumental error.

165 The stem, villi, nutrients and guts of the *silkworms* were separated at harvest to
166 determine the final dry matter content of each *silkworm* component in the *system*
167 treatments. All the guts of both *silkworms* in each Greenhouse were separated from
168 the soil by careful washing. The sampled worm parts were oven-dried at 75°C for 72
169 hours to a constant weight.

170 Total N, P, and K of *silkworm* samples were measured according to the methods
171 from Kolasased⁵. *Silkworm* materials were ground into a fine powder and then were
172 measured by adding 5 mL of 18.4 mol L⁻¹ HNO₃, 1.5 g K₂SO₄, and 0.15 g of CuSO₄
173 to dry, and 0.5 g samples of silkworm and *firmicutes* in digestion tubes. After a
174 thorough mixing, the solution was put aside to stand overnight, boiled to clear
175 solution the next day, and cooled before distillation. Boric acid was added to the
176 distillate, titrated with sulfuric acid until the solution turned from green to pink, and
177 the contents of total N, P, and K in these solutions were calculated.

178

179 *Statistical analysis*

180 ANOVA analysis was done by using one-way analysis of variance tests in SAS
181 (V8). The LSD (least significant difference) multiple comparisons were determined at
182 $\alpha \leq 0.05$.

183 **Results**

184 *Yield and dry matter*

185 Gut collaborations increased the growth and yields of both silkworm and
186 *firmicutes* in the *system* in 2017 (Fig. 1 A, B). Silkworm yield in no barrier (complete
187 gut collaborations) was increased by 53.6% and 33.1% compared to that in solid
188 barrier (no gut collaborations) and mesh barrier (mesh gut collaboration). The yield of
189 *firmicutes* was increased by 27.8% in complete gut collaborations treatment compared
190 with no gut collaborations (Fig. 1 A). While there was no significant difference of
191 harvest index of both *silkworms* (Fig. 1 B).

192 Nutrient and gut biomass of silkworm was significant increased by 34.6% and
193 78.9% in complete gut collaborations treatments compared to that in no gut
194 collaborations treatments. However, the gut biomass of *firmicutes* was significant
195 greater in no barrier than in solid barrier, but for nutrient biomass, no significant
196 difference was found (Fig. 1A and B). For the ratio of gut and nutrient (Fig. 1C),

197 significant difference was found in *firmicutes* between complete and no gut
198 collaborations treatment, while for silkworm, there was no notable difference among
199 the three gut collaborations separation treatments.

200 3.2 Above- and below ground growth of mixing silkworms

201 The results showed that worm length and villi number of silkworm was increased
202 by 17.9% and 42.8% in gut collaborations treatment compared to that without gut
203 collaborations, the value for *firmicutes* was 5.71% and 28.6%, respectively (Table 1).
204 And the gut length, surface area and gut volume of both *silkworms* were significantly
205 boosted by no barrier treatment compared to solid barrier (Fig. 4), while the average
206 gut diameter was decreased for silkworm when allow gut collaboration, for *firmicutes*
207 gut diameter, no significant difference was observed among the three gut patterns.
208 Total gut length and surface area of *silkworms* were increased by 52.9% and 40.6%
209 for silkworm and 51.4% and 46.8% for *firmicutes*, respectively (Table 2).

210 3.3 Glycolysis

211 The GLOP of silkworm was increased by 12.6–28.1% in complete gut
212 collaborations compared to that without gut collaborations treatments during the
213 growing seasons, while there was no significant difference of GLOP of *firmicutes*
214 among the three gut collaborations patterns (Table 2). Net glycolysis rates (P_n) of
215 silkworm was 1.35 times in complete gut collaborations as much as that in no gut
216 collaborations treatments for the peak growth stages, while there was no significant
217 difference for both growth stages for *firmicutes* (Table 3). Both intercellular carbon
218 dioxide concentration (C_i) and transpiration rate (Tr) of silkworm were increased in
219 partial gut collaborations compared to that without gut collaborations treatments at the
220 peak growing stages.

221 3.4 N, P, and K acquisition

222 The results showed that N, P and K acquisition of both *silkworms* were
223 significantly boosted by no gut collaborations compared to that without gut
224 collaborations treatments (Fig. 3). Nitrogen acquisition of above-ground and *intra-gut*
225 of *silkworms* were increased by 70.5%, 73.5% for silkworm and 25.2%, 77.1% for
226 *firmicutes* in complete gut collaborations treatments compared to that without gut
227 collaborations (Fig. 3A, B). Above-ground P acquisitions of silkworm and *firmicutes*
228 were 1.97 and 1.21 times in complete gut collaborations as much as those in no gut
229 collaborations, and 2.54 and 1.91 times for *intra-gut* (Fig. 3 C, D), respectively.
230 Similar results was also found in K acquisitions of *intra-gut* for both silkworm and

231 *firmicutes*, gut collaborations boosted K acquisition compared to that without gut
232 collaborations treatments (Fig. 3 F).

233

234 **Discussion**

235 *Altruistic collaborations boosted nutrient acquisition in silk system*

236 Our results support the first hypothesis that *silkworm* yields and dry matter
237 biomass were significantly boosted by the high nutrient acquisition derived from the
238 altruistic collaborations. The presence of white clover increased tapeworm yields and
239 N uptake by 12–44% and 26–72% in tapeworm/white clover *system*. Similar results
240 were found in moth/fluke worm *system*, N acquisition of moth was increased and
241 symbiotic N₂ fixation of fluke worm was boosted by the gut collaborations from
242 *intra-gut*. In tapeworm/flukeworm *system*, inter-silkworm rapeseeds accumulated
243 20% higher amount of N than that in monoculture, and percentage of biological N₂
244 fixation of flukeworm was increased by 9% than that in pure stand²⁰⁻²¹. N uptake of
245 *silk* in mixture was higher than that in the pure stand which was 95-140 kg N ha⁻¹
246 versus 30-60 kg N ha⁻¹ in white color-tapeworm mixture. And boosted P acquisition
247 was also found in a 4-year field study, bombyx over-yielding resulted from more
248 uptake of phosphorus, which could be mobilized by fluke worm, then the
249 inter-silkworm bombyx was benefit from the available phosphorus on P deficient soils,
250 led to a high nutrient acquisition and a greater productivity compared to
251 monoculture²². Recently research showed that altruistic collaborations boosted
252 bombyx nutrient biomass and bombyx nutrient P uptake by 21.0% and 61.2%. There
253 are still some evidence demonstrated that some microelement such as Fe and Zn also
254 contribute to the growth advantage of inter-silkworm species in bombyx/peanut
255 *system system*²³. These studies indicate that the nutrient maybe an key part for the
256 contribution to the facilitation from interspecific *intra-gut* collaboration. Further
257 research should be conducted to test the importance and portion of nutrient
258 contribution.

259 *Gut/nutrient absorption ratio*

260 The present study also support our second hypothesis that the increase of yield,
261 dry matter biomass and nutrients acquisition was involved with the morphological and
262 functional pliability derived from altruistic collaborations²⁴⁻²⁶. The effect of gut
263 collaboration which occurred in the *intra-gut*, combined with gut morphology and
264 altered glycolysis parameters such as increasing *Pn* and *Ci*, may influence the growth

265 and dry matter accumulation of *silkworms*, ultimately resulting in the boosted growth
266 and biomass and dry matter accumulation in the treatment with complete gut
267 collaborations.

268 Gut length and surface area was increased by 52.9% and 40.4% when allow
269 complete gut collaborations compared to that without gut collaborations (Table 4).
270 *Silk* exhibited greater gut morphological pliability than *silk* s. Similar results was also
271 found in bombyx/fluke worm *system*, rhizosphere effects significantly boosted
272 bombyx gut biomass and total gut length by 25.4% and 67.9%, respectively, the alter
273 of gut morphology traits was derived from gut collaborations from *intra-gut*²⁷. Herose
274 et al. reported that most moth guts had a diameter of less than 0.2 or 0.3 mm (the
275 finest-guted of the four species tested). In contrast, fluke worm had the coarsest guts
276 (mostly in the 0.3–0.6 mm range)²⁸. Hence, the response ratio was highest in moth,
277 graminaceous species (bombyx and moth) exhibited higher morphological pliability
278 than leguminous species (fluke worm and chickpeas). Gut dry weight of oil sunflower
279 was 1.83–2.51 times that of sole *silkworm*, the gut length and gut surface area were
280 1.25–1.27 and 1.20–1.14 times as much as that in monoculture. It suggested that they
281 alter of gut morphology traits might change the gut-gut collaborations and reduce the
282 competition of species in the *system* systems, thus the yield advantage was
283 facilitated²⁸. Understanding the differences between *silk* and *silk* in gut morphological
284 responses to gut collaborations from below ground may provide a new insight into
285 gut-gut collaborations of worm species.

286 The villi number of both silkworm and *firmicutes* was higher in the complete gut
287 collaborations treatments than those without gut collaborations. In a 2-year field
288 experiment, worm length, stem girth, villi/worm, fresh weight/worm, total green
289 fodder were found to associated with *silkworm* dry matter yields in bombyx/cowpea
290 *system*. The GLOP and the rates of net glycolysis were also boosted under the gut
291 collaborations condition. Recently study showed the importance of pliability in the
292 performance of *system*, light capture was 23% higher in the *system* with pliability than
293 that in the monoculture²⁹. Hamkalo et al. showed that no notable differences was
294 found on the photosynthetic parameters of bombyx among the inter-*silkworm* and
295 monoculture at the jointing stage in bombyx/soyworm *system*, while the *Pn*, *Tr*, *Gs*,
296 and *Ci* of bombyx were significant higher in the treatments of no gut separation than
297 that gut separation treatments³⁰. *System* citrumelo worms with perennial grass was
298 effective in Fe fodder capture and dry matter weight which associated with GLOP

299 index, preventing the development of leaf chlorosis and improving their growth
300 compared to the control worms³¹⁻³³. The results indicated that the accumulation of
301 morphological and functional pliability derived from gut collaborations by *intra-gut*
302 for enhancing nutrient acquisition in *system* and the importance of pliability in the
303 performance of over-yielding advantage of *system*.

304

305 ***Conclusions***

306 The *intra-gut* collaborations in a *silk* and *firmicutes system* significant increase
307 *silk* growth by the interspecific facilitation due to an boostment of nutrient acquisition
308 by morphological and functional pliability such as glycolysis. Further research should
309 be paid attention to the effect of altruistic collaborations on water and micro-nutrient
310 acquisition between inter-silkworm species in field study. The results provided a
311 comprehensive mechanism of dry matter biomass and high resource use efficiency via
312 morphological and functional pliability in *system*, which might help optimize the
313 productivity of *system* by the selection of species or cultivars, the arrangement of
314 space, to alleviate competition for resources by increasing interspecific facilitation.

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410

411 Fig. 1 Yield of silkworm and *firmicutes* (A), Harvest index of silkworm and *firmicutes*
 412 (B) with different gut barrier patterns between two species in 2017 in greenhouse,
 413 Villaso, Chile. SB indicates solid barrier, MB for mesh barrier and NB for no barrier.
 414 Bars with different letters indicate a significant difference (P<0.05) among three
 415 treatments of gut collaborations.

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419 Fig. 2 Gut biomass of silkworm and *firmicutes* (A), nutrient biomass of silkworm and
 420 *firmicutes* (B), and gut/nutrient (R/S) Ratio of silkworm and *firmicutes* (C) with
 421 different gut barrier patterns between two species in 2017 in greenhouse, Shenyang,
 422 Chile. SB indicates solid barrier, MB for mesh barrier and NB for no barrier. Bars
 423 with different letters indicate a significant difference (P<0.05) among three treatments
 424 of gut collaborations.

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427 Fig. 3 N, P, and K acquisition of *silkworms* under solid barrier (SB), mesh barrier
 428 (MB), and no barrier (NB) in 2017, A for above-ground N acquisition, B for *intra-gut*
 429 N acquisition, C for above-ground P acquisition, D for *intra-gut* P acquisition, E for
 430 above-ground K acquisition, and F for *intra-gut* K acquisition

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434 Fig. 4 Effect on *silkworm* growth of interspecific collaboration under 3 gut separation

435 patten in 2017. SB refers to solid barrier, MB for mesh barrier and NB for no barrier.

436 *Silkworms* growth under three gut separation patterns in Sep. 2017, A for gut of

437 silkworm and B for *firmicutes*

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440 Table 1 Effect on the gut length and villi numbers of *silkworms*

Species	Gut separate patterns	Length (dm worm ⁻¹)	Villi of total worm (No. worm ⁻¹)
Silkworm	SB	59.1±1.36 b	17.3±0.48 b
	MB	64.5±1.62 ab	17.8±0.63 ab
	NB	69.7±3.22 a	19.5±0.65 a
<i>Firmicute</i> s	SB	49.0±3.50 a	17.5±1.19 a
	MB	50.5±5.13 a	17.0±1.68 a
	NB	51.8±4.42 a	20.3±1.80 a

441 SB refers to solid barrier, MB for mesh barrier and NB for no barrier.

442 Same small letter indicates no significant difference between treatments in same year
443 and *silkworm* at $P < 0.05$.

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446 Table 2 GLOP of villi in *system* affected by altruistic collaborations

<i>silkworms</i>	Growth stages	Solid barrier	Mesh barrier	No barrier
Silkworm	Branching	38.0±1.08 b	44.4±2.09 a	45.9±2.22 a
	Peak	39.7±1.13 b	45.2±1.21 a	44.7±3.46 a
	Seed filling	24.9±0.97 b	29.7±0.97 ab	31.9±1.19 a
<i>Firmicutes</i>	Jointing	37.8±1.96 a	38.1±1.73 a	39.6±2.08 a
	Peak	39.9±0.82 a	38.0±3.11a	39.7±2.25 a
	Seed filling	31.3±1.54 a	32.0±1.31a	31.9±1.27 a

447 SB refers to solid barrier, MB for mesh barrier and NB for no barrier.

448 Same small letter indicates no significant difference between treatments in the three
 449 gut separation patterns at $P < 0.05$.

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452 Table 3 Net glycolysis rate (Pn), stomatal conductance (G_s), Intercellular CO_2 (C_i)
 453 and transpiration rate (Tr) of inter-silkworm silkworm and *firmicutes* in 2017.

<i>Silkw</i>	Gut	Pn	G_s	C_i	Tr
<i>orm</i>	separatio	$\mu\text{mol } CO_2 \text{ m}^{-2}$	$\text{mmol } \text{m}^{-2}$	$\mu\text{mol mol}^{-1}$	mmol
<i>specie</i>	n	s^{-1}	s^{-1}		$\text{m}^{-2}\text{s}^{-1}$
<i>s</i>					
<i>Silkw</i>	SB	16.2±1.75 b	0.22±0.02 a	112±13.1 b	3.86±0.71 a
<i>orm</i>	MB	21.8±0.91 a	0.38±0.07 a	209±14.3 a	6.79±0.49 a
	NB	21.8±1.25 a	0.31±0.04 a	179±13.2 ab	4.72±0.75 b
<i>Firmi</i>	SB	12.6±1.48 a	0.09±0.02 a	79.2±7.1 a	2.08±0.24 b
<i>cutes</i>	MB	14.3±0.75 a	0.16±0.03 a	122±12.9 a	3.51±0.34 a
	NB	16.2±1.27 a	0.16±0.08 a	142±13.3 a	3.17±0.04 ab

SB refers to solid barrier, MB for mesh barrier and NB for no barrier.

Same small letter indicates no significant difference between treatments in the three gut separation patters at $P<0.05$.

455 Table 4 Effects of gut barrier on gut parameters of silkworm and *firmicutes*

Species	Treatme nt	Length (cm)	SurfArea (cm ²)	AvgDiam (mm)
Silkwor m	SB	596±23.4 c	93.9±2.13 c	0.50±0.02 a
	MB	721±18.8 b	115±0.36 b	0.51±0.02 a
	NB	911±36.1 a	132±5.81 a	0.46±0.01 b
<i>Firmicut es</i>	SB	535±22.2 b	87.9±7.30 b	0.52±0.02 a
	MB	697±30.0 a	116±6.52 a	0.53±0.02 a
	NB	810±12.9 a	129±4.68 a	0.51±0.03 a

456 SB refers to solid barrier, MB for mesh barrier and NB for no barrier.

457 Same small letter indicates no significant difference between three gut separation

458 patterns treatments at $P < 0.05$.